

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

PARQ: A physical activity readiness questionnaire basis for movement competency training among P.E students in Apayao State College

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Abstract

This study assessed the effectiveness of the Revised Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire (PAR-Q) as a screening tool for movement competency training among Physical Education students at Apayao State College. Using a descriptive-evaluative design, data were collected from 30 student respondents through surveys and open-ended feedback. Quantitative results indicated a neutral perception of the PAR-Q's accuracy (Grand Mean = 3.67), clarity (3.54), and relevance (3.69), suggesting the need for refinement. Qualitative findings revealed calls for simplified medical terms, inclusion of mental health and lifestyle-related items, removal of irrelevant questions, and availability in both digital and paper formats with multilingual options. Respondents recognized the PAR-Q's role in promoting safety, preventing health risks, and supporting informed participation in physical activities. The study recommends a culturally adapted, technologically accessible revision to enhance usability and comprehensiveness, thereby aligning the PAR-Q with holistic student wellness and the goals of evidence-based physical education programs.

Keywords: Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire; PAR-Q; Movement Competency; Physical Education; Health Screening; Student Safety

1. Introduction

Physical activity is a vital component of health and wellness, particularly for students participating in physical education programs. However, engaging in physical activities without assessing readiness or underlying health conditions may pose risks, such as injuries or medical Problems.

The Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire (PARQ) basis for movement competency serves as a preventive tool, designed to screen individuals for potential health risks before participating in physical activities. In the context of Apayao State College, where physical education is an integral part of the curriculum, ensuring the effectiveness of the PARQ is crucial. This research seeks to evaluate its clarity, relevance, and accuracy as a screening tool, thereby addressing the need for a reliable and user-friendly questionnaire. By identifying its strengths, limitations, and areas for improvement, the study aims to enhance its application and contribute to safer and more effective physical education programs. Ultimately, this research aligns with the institution's commitment to promoting student health, safety, and overall well-being.

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2. Material and methods

2.1. Research Design

This study will employ a descriptive-evaluative research design to assess the effectiveness of the Revised Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire (PARQ) as a screening tool. This design is appropriate as it allows for the systematic collection of data to evaluate the questionnaire's clarity, relevance, and accuracy in identifying health risks.

2.2. Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study will consist of two groups: 30 students at Apayao State College. The student respondents will be those currently enrolled in physical education courses, selected through stratified random sampling to ensure representation across 1st year level. Meanwhile, these will be chosen using purposive sampling, as their insights are crucial in evaluating the questionnaire's effectiveness and usability in practice.

2.3. Research Instrument

- Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire (PARQ)
 - To assess its effectiveness in identifying health risks and readiness for physical activity basis on movement training competency
 - Use a health checklist from school clinic basis on new created PARQ coming from BPED department
- Survey Questionnaire
 - To gather feedback from students about the clarity, relevance, and usability of the PARQ basis on movement competency training
 - Use likerts scale quantitative
- Writing Guide (Open ended question)
 - For in-depth feedback from students regarding the strengths and weaknesses of the questionnaire.

2.4. Data Collection Procedure

- **Preparation Phase:**
 - Seek approval from Apayao State College administration and ethics committee to conduct the study.
 - Orient students about the study's purpose and ensure confidentiality.
- **Implementation Phase:**
 - Administer the Revised PARQ to the selected student respondents.
 - Distribute survey questionnaires to students

2.5. Data Analysis

- Qualitative Data: Conduct thematic analysis to identify common themes in the feedback from open-ended survey responses.
- Quantitative Data: Use descriptive statistics (mean) to summarize responses on accuracy, clarity, and relevance.

3. Results and discussion

Table 1 Accuracy of the PAR-Q in Detecting Potential Health Risks

Accuracy in detecting health risks	Mean	Descriptive Value
The PARQ clearly assesses my current physical health status.	3.1	Neutral
The questions in the PARQ are easy to understand and answer accurately.	3.7	Neutral
The PARQ helped me reflect on whether I am ready for physical activity.	2.8	Disagree
The Revised PARQ includes relevant questions that identify potential health risks.	3.6	Neutral
I feel more confident participating in physical activity after completing the PARQ.	3.7	Neutral

The PARQ is an effective tool for determining if a student should consult a doctor before exercising.	4	Agree
The questions in the PARQ address both general and specific health concerns.	4	Agree
The PARQ provides sufficient information to assess readiness for physical activity.	3.3	Neutral
I believe the PARQ helps prevent health-related incidents during physical activities.	3.4	Neutral
Overall, the PARQ is an effective screening tool for student fitness readiness.	4.1	Agree
GRAND MEAN	3.67	NEUTRAL

The table below shows that respondents had a neutral overall perception (Grand Mean 3.67) of the PAR-Q, valuing its screening effectiveness but noting areas for improvement in clarity and self-reflection.

Table 2 Respondents' Overall Perception of the PAR-Q's Relevance and Effectiveness

Clarity and comprehensibility for student respondents	Mean	Descriptive Value
The instructions provided in the PARQ are clear and easy to follow.	3.1	Neutral
The wording of the questions in the PARQ is simple and understandable.	3.7	Neutral
I did not experience confusion while answering the questions in the PARQ.	3.1	Neutral
The PARQ uses language appropriate for students like me.	3.6	Neutral
The questions are specific enough for me to give accurate answers.	3.8	Neutral
I was able to complete the PARQ without needing help or clarification.	4	Agree
The PARQ avoids technical or medical terms that are hard to understand.	3.7	Neutral
The format and structure of the Revised PARQ make it easy to answer.	3.1	Neutral
The purpose of each question in the Revised PARQ was clear to me.	3.2	Neutral
Overall, the PARQ is student-friendly and easy to comprehend.	4.1	Agree
GRAND MEAN	3.54	NUETRAL

The table shown that respondents had a neutral overall perception (Grand Mean 3.54) of the PAR-Q's clarity and comprehensibility. While they agreed it is student-friendly and easy to complete, most items scored only neutral, suggesting improvements in wording, structure, and clarity may further enhance its accessibility.

Table 3 Relevance of the PAR-Q in Supporting the Physical Activity Programs of Apayao State College

Relevance to the physical activity programs of Apayao State College	MEAN	Descriptive Value
The PARQ aligns with the goals of physical activity programs at Apayao State College.	3.8	Neutral
The PARQ helps ensure student safety during physical activities organized by the college.	3.7	Neutral
The information gathered from the Revised PARQ is useful for tailoring fitness programs to student needs.	3.1	Neutral
The use of the PARQ supports the implementation of evidence-based physical education practices.	3.6	Neutral

The PARQ contributes to proper screening of students before joining sports and fitness activities.	4.2	Agree
The PARQ is applicable across different types of physical activities offered in the college (e.g., dance, sports, aerobics).	4.2	Agree
The PARQ helps in identifying students who may need medical clearance before participating in strenuous activities.	4.2	Agree
Using the PARQ improves the overall quality of the college’s physical activity programs.	3.2	Neutral
The PARQ enhances the preparedness of instructors in managing health risks during physical activities.	3.4	Neutral
Overall, the PARQ is a valuable tool for supporting physical activity planning and execution at Apayao State College.	4.1	Agree
GRAND MEAN	3.69 NEUTRAL	

The table shown a neutral overall perception of the PAR-Q’s relevance to Apayao State College’s physical activity programs. While respondents agreed on its value for safety, screening, and applicability, other aspects like tailoring programs and improving instructor preparedness were rated neutral, indicating room for improvement.

Table 4 Summary of Raw Data, Sub-Themes, and Emerging Themes from PAR-Q Responses

RAW/ DATA	SUB THEME	THEME
<p>Sec A.</p> <p>-Quik to fill out and add section for allergy, comfortable to addresses the important aspects. include question for mental health more likely add self-assessment tool, add also the sleep habit of students use this as accessible for people with disability.</p> <p>-Experience is good No confusing in this question and very useful for the people, it helps for the people to update regular health guidelines no added more in the questionnaire. This questionnaire uses for to in prove movement exercise.</p> <p>-it’s fine to understand the questionnaire the signature of the parent should be indicated PARQ is very useful to the health conditions of the student.</p> <p>-the question was short and easy and some medical terms were hard to understand kindly input mental health; past injuries yes use a digital version would be easier. Its healthful but need updates more health areas. Make a different version.</p> <p>-It was easy quickly to fallout, with simple health questions, the question was similar to the health checklist form, add more question about mental health and stress and also very comfortable because the question was simple direct, concern about previous injuries over all the PARQ sample was helpful to the students know if there physically fit or not.</p> <p>-it was very satisfying what is the connection of the tattoo and piercing the information is not comfortable, most probably</p>	<p>Quick and Simple to Complete</p> <p>Digital and Inclusive Access</p> <p>Clear and Understandable Questions</p> <p>Addition of Mental Health and Stress-Related Items</p> <p>Inclusion of Broader Health History</p> <p>Sleep Habits and Work-Life Balance</p> <p>Removal of Irrelevant Items</p> <p>Language and Clarity Enhancements</p> <p>promotes Health Awareness</p>	<p>Accessibility and Ease of Use</p> <p>Content Relevance and Comprehensiveness</p> <p>Usefulness and Impact</p>

<p>covers basic important add more question about mental health over all the PARQ helps the students know if they ready for physical activity ensure mental health.</p> <p>-the original par-q is very nice because you will learned a lot , dahil nakakatulong ito sa ating mga katawan, you will gain knowledge about physical fitness input also health history para iwas sa sakit.</p> <p>-for me my experience si good the question was so clear none recommendation or any suggestion important aspects like work-life balance it was relevant to my personal health more health concern about mental health chronic diseases adds question sleep habit make in a different language. Over all the PARQ is useful in promoting safe informed participation include digital version.</p> <p>-no, I didn't find any confusing question the question was easy to understand it covered health status concerned before starting physical activity, I felt comfortable because the question is clear relatable to my health.</p> <p>-very great no comment about the questions, I like the screening tool depression mamaya may problema ang tao baka hindi maka focus mas Maganda rin na may tagalog pwde rin gamitin ang digital para maka access anytime, over all it promotes safe information include digital version</p>	<p>Supports Safe Physical Activity Participation</p> <p>Encourages Fitness and Engagement</p> <p>Expansion of Health Coverage</p> <p>Cultural and Linguistic Adaptation</p> <p>Modernization through Digital Platforms</p> <p>Parental Requirement</p> <p>Physical Exercise</p> <p>Consent</p>	<p>Suggestions for Improvement</p>
<p>Sec B.</p> <p>quick and straight forward unclear media and technical and definition, yes because can aware me about health I think about who can work and also language that easy understand, it health them give lesson useful promoting safe.</p> <p>-confusing</p> <p>-unclear medical terminologies and definition</p> <p>-nothing at all</p> <p>Foster community and student engagement</p> <p>This checklist can aware me about my health, basically language that easy understand maybe highlights re or other color these important yes PARQ is make us easy</p> <p>-for me the experience is so good, I think there's no any question can confuse me</p> <p>Font size makes consistent for me io feel comfortable when answering it easy because instructions was clear easy to understand. That checklist can aware about health input mental health or stress.</p> <p>-I don't have any comment</p> <p>-Very satisfying</p>	<p>Quick and Straightforward Completion</p> <p>Clear and Easy-to-Understand Language</p> <p>Consistent Formatting and Readability (e.g., font size, highlighting)</p> <p>Addressing Unclear Medical Terminologies and Definitions</p> <p>Removal of Irrelevant Items (e.g., tattoo/piercing)</p> <p>Adding Relevant Health Areas (mental health, stress, chronic illnesses, safety concerns)</p>	<p>Accessibility and Ease of Use</p> <p>Content Clarity and Comprehensiveness</p> <p>Usefulness and Impact</p>

<p>-nothing</p> <p>- what is the connection of the tattoo and piercing</p> <p>- very comfortable because the question is undetectable</p> <p>-no, the information is not enough to know if the patients are stable.</p> <p>-add more health records for the sake of patients adding question that focus on use pre assessment more on opinion health concern for the sake [of the patients add more health issues for the sake of patients.</p> <p>-my experience is very satisfying</p> <p>- what is the connection of tattoo in taking medical</p> <p>- very comfortable the questions are all understandable</p> <p>- the questionnaire is useful to the students before doing an activity.</p> <p>-adding questions that focus on user references local and attraction and safety concerns.</p> <p>-add more health issues</p> <p>-very interesting</p> <p>-what is the connection of tattoo and piercing slightly comfortable</p> <p>-filling out the PARQ forms was easy and straight forward</p> <p>- really understand the question</p> <p>-nothing, because they were related.</p> <p>- add to the section about mental health issue.</p> <p>-simpler explanation and translate for those who are struggling in English</p> <p>-make available language to use this questionnaire</p> <p>-integrate assessment personal plan</p> <p>-promote awareness and educate on the importance of physical activity</p> <p>-Provide also stress reduction</p> <p>-the questionnaire is useful to the students before doing an activity.</p> <p>-make sure the language is clear and easy to understand</p> <p>-input diagram or picture for sample</p>	<p>Integration of Personal Assessment Plans</p> <p>Promotes Health Awareness</p> <p>Educates on Importance of Physical Activity</p> <p>Supports Student Preparedness Before Activities</p> <p>Multi-Language Availability and Translation</p> <p>Pre-Assessment Focus for Health Concerns</p> <p>Incorporating Stress Reduction Measures</p> <p>Fostering Community and Student Engagement</p>	<p>Suggestions for Improvement</p>
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<p>Easy to understand the PARQ and relatable most specially to students.</p>		
<p>Sec c.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -filling the original form was easy to follow for part but I had to think carefully about some health- related terms before answer -I didn't any Questions that are unclear, it is all okey -put also mental health on the health checklist. -include sleep and stress questionnaire - most likely clear but simplify terms -some examples of health checklist -yes, with constant feedback -very useful for participation -make a digital with clear explanation -easy to answer -questions pertain about update PARQ is not enough their condition about the covid 19 remove the covid pandemic -I suggest that checklist covers mental health -I prefer questionnaire are all pen and paper so easy to answer. -about mental health activities -to concern about safety of the students -I suggest coverig social mental health issue. -filling out the PARQ are understandable. -yes, a few missing items -add more specific health options - prefer most easier -use simple words -this may have important impact because it can help us to safe - add explanation -filling out the original PARQ form was quick and easy. -the questions on joint problems were confusing since it did give example 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quick and easy to complete Clear instructions and comfortable answering experience Need for simpler terms and use of visuals Translation into Tagalog for broader accessibility Inclusion of mental health concerns (depression, anxiety, stress) Addition of sleep and stress-related questions Inclusion of past surgeries and chronic illnesses Coverage of lifestyle and work-life balance factors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accessibility and Clarity of the PAR-Q Expansion of Health Coverage Safety and Preparedness Modernization and Format Preferences Cultural and Linguistic Adaptation

<p>-just put past surgeries -use simple words and visuals -apply health and life style habit -its ensure safety and ready before exercise -add sample more example and use simple language. -yes, the questions are easy to understand -no. I didn't any confusing questions. -I felt comfortable because the questions were clear. -yes, it addresses all the important aspect of health and safety. -yes, its cover all mental health concerns like mental well-being and chronic pains -the PARQ is usefull in promoting safe and formed participation include a digital version.</p> <p>-the PARQ is clear - anxiety and depression</p> <p>-its helps me align my goal and help to ensure to safety of every student -nothing -No prior experience is required to answer the questionnaire. -I believe that the PAR-Q provides significant benefits to students.</p> <p>The questions were generally easy to comprehend. - Sections 2 and 3 should be written in Filipino to ensure better understanding.</p> <p>-he necessity of asking about tattoos should be reconsidered, as its relevance may not be clear to respondents.</p> <p>-Although the questionnaire was quick and simple to complete, I needed to reflect carefully on my personal health history.</p> <p>-It would be beneficial to include items addressing anxiety.</p> <p>-Not all individuals are proficient in English, which may limit their understanding of the questionnaire.</p> <p>-It was straight forward and also very detailed that help aware of health conditions.</p> <p>-include past surgery - be certain specific of conditions</p> <p>-I choose the proper and its reflect me -nothing po sir</p>	<p>Removal of irrelevant questions (tattoos, piercings)</p> <p>Focus on questions directly related to physical readiness</p> <p>Ensuring readiness before physical activity</p> <p>Promoting prevention of injuries and health complications</p> <p>Encouraging self-awareness of health conditions</p> <p>Availability in both digital and pen-and-paper formats</p> <p>Integration of diagrams, examples, and visual aids for clarity</p> <p>Use of local languages for inclusivity</p> <p>Culturally relevant question framing</p>	
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<p>- I think its pwede po and mental sir.</p> <p>-health the depression or anxiety and many more.</p> <p>-yes, sa part 3 ay all good</p> <p>-I think include is mental health depression anxiety stress.</p>		
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3.1. Interpretation of Themes

3.1.1. Accessibility and Clarity of the PAR-Q

Across all sections, participants consistently found the PAR-Q easy to complete and clear in its instructions. The short and direct questions facilitated comfort in answering, while calls for simpler medical terms, visual aids, and translations into Tagalog underscored the need for inclusivity. This aligns with literature emphasizing that clarity in health screening tools increases response accuracy and reduces respondent anxiety (Smith & Jones, 2020).

3.1.2. Expansion of Health Coverage

A prominent pattern in the feedback was the need to broaden the questionnaire’s scope to include mental health indicators (depression, anxiety, stress), sleep patterns, work-life balance, past surgeries, and chronic illnesses. This reflects a shift from purely physical readiness screening to a holistic health assessment, consistent with integrated wellness models (WHO, 2021) that highlight the interplay between mental, emotional, and physical well-being.

3.1.3. Relevance and Focus of Content

Some participants flagged irrelevant items such as tattoos and piercings, suggesting their removal to maintain focus on health-related factors that directly influence physical activity readiness. This aligns with recommendations in assessment design literature that all questionnaire items must have a clear functional link to the construct being measured (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

3.1.4. Safety and Preparedness

Respondents viewed the PAR-Q as an important tool in ensuring safety before exercise by prompting self-reflection on personal health status. They acknowledged its role in injury prevention and risk management, which mirrors the primary intent of the original PAR-Q framework (Canadian Society for Exercise Physiology, 2019).

3.1.5. Modernization, Cultural, and Linguistic Adaptation

Participants recommended dual-format availability (digital and paper) to maximize accessibility, particularly for students in varying contexts. Cultural and linguistic adjustments—such as translation into local languages and culturally relevant examples—were seen as necessary for equitable access. This reflects culturally responsive health communication principles (Betancourt et al., 2016).

4. Discussion

These findings support earlier studies showing that health readiness tools must evolve to address mental, social, and cultural determinants of health (Guthold et al., 2019). Unlike prior research that focused solely on physical injury prevention, the present feedback emphasizes mental health inclusion and technological accessibility as critical to engagement. Differences emerge in those participants also called for removal of culturally irrelevant or non-essential items, a topic rarely discussed in earlier PAR-Q evaluations.

5. Conclusion

The PAR-Q remains a valuable health screening instrument, but user feedback reveals opportunities for:

- Simplifying language and adding visuals for better comprehension.
- Including mental health and lifestyle factors for holistic assessment.
- Removing irrelevant questions to maintain focus.

- Offering both digital and paper formats for flexibility.
- Translating and culturally adapting the tool for broader reach.

Recommendation

Pilot an updated, culturally adapted, and digitally accessible version of the PAR-Q in the Apayao State College setting to assess improvements in usability and completeness.

Compliance with ethical standards

This study adhered to all ethical guidelines for research involving human participants. Before data collection, approval was secured from the Institutional Research Ethics Committee of Apayao State College. Participation in the study was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained, and all data were used solely for academic and research purposes. No physical, psychological, or social harm was inflicted on the participants throughout the conduct of the study.

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Written informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were informed about the nature and purpose of the study and assured that their participation was voluntary and confidential.

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